

**IN THE MIAMI COUNTY COMMON PLEAS COURT
MIAMI COUNTY, OHIO**

LVNV FUNDING, LLC 55 Beattie Place (Suite 110) Greenville, SC 29601 PLAINTIFF v. SHEILA WARREN AKA SHEILA POTTER 7925 Union Shelby Road Piqua, OH 45356 DEFENDANT	CASE NUMBER 24 CV 00196 [TRANSFERRED CASE NUMBER 2024CVF00581] JUDGE STACY WALL NOTICE OF FILING EXPERT REPORT
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NOTICE OF FILING EXPERT REPORT

COMES NOW Defendant, Shelia Warren (hereinafter, "Defendant" or "Warren" and in accordance with Ohio R. Civ. P. 26 and any applicable orders entered by this Honorable Court, hereby files Defendant's Notice of Filing Expert Report, thereby providing notice to this Honorable Court and all Parties to this action that the following was filed and made of record in the above-captioned matter:

Please take notice that attached hereto are:

- (a) Joint Expert Report of Brian Sullivan and Sam Han, Ph.D.; and
- (b) Curriculum Vitae of Brian Sullivan; and
- (c) Curriculum Vitae of Sam Han.

[SIGNATURE TO FOLLOW]

Respectfully submitted on 2025-February-28.

/s/ Andrew Barnes
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**IN THE MIAMI COUNTY COMMON PLEAS COURT
MIAMI COUNTY, OHIO**

<p>LVNV FUNDING, LLC 55 Beattie Place (Suite 110) Greenville, SC 29601</p> <p style="text-align: center;">PLAINTIFF</p> <p style="text-align: center;">v.</p> <p>SHEILA WARREN AKA SHEILA POTTER 7925 Union Shelby Road Piqua, OH 45356</p> <p style="text-align: center;">DEFENDANT</p>	<p>CASE NUMBER 24 CV 00196</p> <p>[TRANSFERRED CASE NUMBER 2024CVF00581]</p> <p>JUDGE STACY WALL</p> <p>CERTIFICATE OF SERVICE AND FILING</p>
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CERTIFICATE OF FILING AND SERVICE

The undersigned counsel certifies that the above-attached document was filed using this Honorable Court's Case Management / Electronic Case Filing ("CM/ECF") system on the date set forth herein, which will serve electronically a Notice of Electronic Filing ("NEF") on all counsel of record in this matter, all of whom have consented to accepting the NEF as electronic service through the Court's CM/ECF, additionally the Plaintiff's Attorneys was served a copy by electronic mail to the addresses bgentry@boydgentrylaw.com & ohio@stengerlaw.com .

[SIGNATURE TO FOLLOW]

Respectfully submitted on 2025-February-28

/s/ Andrew Barnes
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**IN THE MIAMI COUNTY COURT OF COMMON PLEAS, OHIO
CIVIL DIVISION**

LVNV FUNDING, LLC PLAINTIFF, v. SHELA WARREN DEFENDANT.	CASE NUMBER 24 CV 00196 JOINT EXPERT REPORT OF BRIAN SULLIVAN AND SAM HAN, PH.D.
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JOINT EXPERT REPORT OF BRIAN SULLIVAN AND SAM HAN, PH.D.

We, Brian Sullivan and Sam Han, declare as follows:

Background and Foundational Statements

- 1.** Both of us are over the age of eighteen years and are competent to make all of the statements in this Joint Expert Report of Brian Sullivan and Sam Han, Ph.D. (hereafter, "Expert Report" or "Report").
- 2.** We voluntarily give the statements in this Report in support of Defendant Sheila Warren (hereafter, "Warren") in the above-captioned proceeding.
- 3.** All statements made herein come from personal knowledge unless stated otherwise or clearly apparent by context.
- 4.** Matters of opinion expressed in this Report are opinions formed based upon our own experiences and knowledge.
- 5.** We declare under penalty of perjury under the laws of the United States of America that, to the best of our knowledge and belief, the statements that are contained in this Report are true and correct.
- 6.** We have been retained as expert witnesses by Counsel for Warren.
- 7.** If there are any statements on which we disagree, those statements are clearly

identified and the reasons for disagreement are clearly stated herein.

Preliminary Statements Relating to Materials Considered

8. We have been advised that Plaintiff LVNV Funding, LLC (hereafter, "LVNV") has not identified an expert and no expert report from LVNV has been provided to us.

9. We do not expect to rely on any expert report from LVNV in forming our opinions herein, however, should LVNV provide an expert report that affects our conclusions herein, then intellectual honesty requires us to review LVNV's expert's report to determine whether our conclusions herein are sound in view of newly discovered information.

Experience and General Background Information for Brian Sullivan

10. In compliance with Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(b), I have provided my most-current curriculum vitae (hereinafter, "CV").

11. I am a member in good standing in the following jurisdictions, bars, or courts:

- a. The Court of Appeals for the Federal Circuit;
- b. The Court of Appeals for the Sixth Circuit;
- c. The United States District Court for the Southern District of Ohio;
- d. The State Bar of Ohio; and
- e. The United States Patent and Trademark Office.

12. I am an attorney in good standing with the State Bar of Ohio and with the Supreme Court of Ohio.

13. I have not been disciplined, sanctioned, or otherwise reprimanded in any jurisdiction where I am licensed to practice.

14. As an Ohio attorney, I am familiar with my ethical obligations under the Ohio R.

Prof. Cond. (hereinafter, "Ethical Rules"), including Ethical Rules 3.3 (Candor Toward the Tribunal).

15. I received my electrical engineering degree and my law degrees from the University of Dayton.

16. Prior to becoming a lawyer, I worked as an engineer for several years.

17. In my work as an attorney, I work regularly with Microsoft® Excel® (hereinafter, "Excel"), Microsoft® Word® (hereinafter, "MSWORD"), and portable document format (hereinafter, "PDF") files.

18. Within the Excel environment, I am familiar with different file extensions, such as ".xls" (original Excel extension), ".xlsx" (Excel with XML (extensible markup language) features, ".csv" (comma-separated values), etc.

19. Furthermore, based on my education, training, and experience, I am familiar with how a spreadsheet can be printed to a PDF file.

Experience and General Background Information for Sam Han, Ph.D.

20. In compliance with Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c), I have provided my most-current CV.

21. I am a member in good standing in the following jurisdictions, bars, or courts:

- a. The Supreme Court of the United States
- b. The Court of Appeals for the Federal Circuit;
- c. The Court of Appeals for the Eleventh Circuit;
- d. The Court of Appeals for the Ninth Circuit;
- e. The Court of Appeals for the Sixth Circuit;

- f. The United States Bankruptcy Appellate Panel for the Tenth Circuit;
- g. The United States District Court for the Northern District of Georgia;
- h. The State Bar of Georgia;
- i. The Supreme Court of Georgia;
- j. The Georgia Court of Appeals; and
- k. The United States Patent and Trademark Office.

22. I am a 2001 graduate of Georgia State University School of Law in Atlanta, Georgia.

23. I have a doctorate (Ph.D.) in Biomedical Engineering from Worcester Polytechnic Institute (hereafter, "WPI").

24. I also have a Master's degree in Biomedical Engineering from WPI.

25. During my time at WPI, I worked with graphics and image processors for sophisticated magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) systems.

26. Also, during my time at WPI, I was the systems administrator for several computer networks, including UNIX-based networks with workstations from Sun Microsystems, Hewlett-Packard, Digital Equipment Corporation (DEC) Alpha, and Silicon Graphics systems, among others.

27. I also have a bachelor's degree in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science from the University of Michigan.

28. Given my educational background and experience, I am familiar with the format of various electronically stored documents and metadata associated with various electronically stored documents, including Microsoft® Excel® spreadsheets.

29. Within the Excel environment, I am familiar with different file extensions, such as ".xls," ".xlsx," ".csv," etc.

30. I have practiced law since 2001.

31. My law practice involves multiple areas of the law, including patent law (where I am required to understand the cutting edge of technology for sophisticated clients) and consumer law (where I represent consumers in debt collection lawsuits as well as in Fair Debt Collection Practices Act lawsuits and counterclaims).

32. I have given professional presentations based on evidence that I have collected from debt-collection cases, which have shown: **(a)** manufactured documents that appear to be original documents; and **(b)** printouts that appear to be from original spreadsheets when they are not.

33. I have been involved in numerous consumer law cases, including (but not limited to) the cases that are listed in my CV.

Compensation Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c)

34. Our billing rate as expert witnesses to evaluate evidence based on electronically stored or electronically transferred documents is \$450 per hour, which we believe to be the normal, customary, and reasonable rate for experts in this area of the law.

35. The reason that \$450/hour is a reasonable and customary rate for reviewing electronically stored files is because the metadata and other hidden information in the electronically stored files are susceptible to corruption and changes unless handled properly, thereby requiring original electronic files to be handled with a certain degree of care or to be saved on an unchangeable medium, such as a compact-disc read-only memory (CDROM).

36. Our billing rates as expert witnesses to evaluate complex business contracts with

multiple sub-parts is \$450 per hour, which we believe to be the normal, customary, and reasonable rate for experts in this area of the law.

37. The reason that \$450/hour is a reasonable and customary rate for reviewing business documents is because such a review requires meticulous attention to detail. The complexity of the documents will become evident from: **(a)** the list of documents themselves; **(b)** the other documents referenced within other documents; and **(c)** the interplay of terms between various cross-referenced documents.

38. In compliance with Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c), we declare that our compensation for this particular case is \$450/hour, which we believe to be a reasonable and customary rate for which we have been retained.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Documents Reviewed

39. In compliance with Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c), we declare that this Report is our complete report, including all of the facts and evidence on which we have relied, along with the methodology that we applied (to the extent that it is not self-evident from the statements herein).

40. We have been retained as experts to review and form an opinion about whether or not the documents produced by LVNV have been altered, destroyed, concealed, or otherwise modified to impair their value as evidence.

41. It is our understanding that the documents that we reviewed included documents that were produced by LVNV.

42. The documents that we reviewed include the following (including all attached exhibits to those documents):

- a. Municipal Court Documents
 - i. LVNV's Complaint with Exhibits, filed 2024-Mar-20.

- ii. Answer, Affirmative Defenses, and Counterclaims.
- iii. Warren's Motion to Dismiss.
- iv. Warren's Motion Relating to Standing.
- v. Warren's Notice of Appearance for Barnes, 2024-Apr-17.
- vi. Warren's Notice of Submission of Discovery Requests.
- vii. Court Notification of Transfer, entered 2024-Apr-30.
- b. Common Pleas Documents
 - i. LVNV's Notice of Appearance by Boyd Gentry, filed 2024-Apr-30.
 - ii. LVNV's Amended Complaint with Exhibits, filed 2024-May-14.
 - iii. LVNV's Reply to Warren's Counterclaim, filed 2024-May-14.
 - iv. LVNV's Summons to Andrew Barnes, 2024-May-15.
 - v. Warren's Answer to Amended Complaint, 2024-Jun-17.
 - vi. Warren's Renewed Motion to Dismiss, 2024-Jun-17.
 - vii. LVNV's Opposition to Warren's Renewed Motion to Dismiss, 2024-Jun-24.
 - viii. Court Order Denying Warren Motion to Dismiss, entered 2024-Jul-15.
 - ix. Court Order Denying Warren Standing Motion, entered 2024-Jul-15.
 - x. LVNV Scheduling Assessment, 2024-Aug-19.
 - xi. Warren Scheduling Assessment, 2024-Aug-21.
 - xii. Warren Expert Disclosure, 2024-Aug-24.
 - xiii. Warren Jury Demand, 2024-Sep-05.
 - xiv. Court Notice of Final Pretrial Conference, 2024-Sep-10.
 - xv. Court Scheduling Order, 2024-Sep-10.

- xvi. Court Trial Procedures Order, 2024-Sep-10.
- xvii. Warren Initial Disclosures, 2024-Oct-09.
- xviii. Warren Motion to Modify Scheduling Order, 2024-Dec-20.
- xix. Court Order Denying Modification of Scheduling Order, 2025-Jan-15.

43. In applying the methodology for our expert opinion, we rely on the documents, facts, data, and LVNV's admissions that are recited herein (hereafter, "Supporting Materials"), all of which we have been made aware of or personally observed.

44. These Supporting Materials are the kinds of facts or data on which experts in this particular field would reasonably rely in forming an opinion on the subject.

Dispelling Commonly Held Misconceptions About Electronic Documents

45. At the outset, there are some commonly held misconceptions that we wish to dispel.

46. By way of background, there are many different types of electronic files, including Microsoft® Excel® spreadsheets (e.g., files with ".xls" or ".xlsx" extensions), Portable Document Format ("PDF") (files with ".pdf" extensions), Microsoft® Word® document (e.g., files with ".doc" or ".docx" extensions), text file (files with ".txt" extensions, comma-separated-value files (e.g., files with ".csv" extensions), etc.

47. These types of electronic files are used in many different environments or fields, including finance, banking, engineering, science, government, schools, personal use, courts, debt collection, etc.

48. The environment in which an electronic file is used does not change the fundamental nature of the electronic file itself.

49. Thus, a Microsoft® Excel® file is an Excel® file when used at a bank; the

Excel® file is an Excel® file when used by a governmental entity; the Excel® file is an Excel® file when used for debt collection; etc.

50. As such, the first common misconception that we wish to dispel is the misconception that an expert for determining whether a particular electronic file has been modified or altered must also be an expert in the particular environment or field where that electronic file is used (e.g., banking, science, etc.); he or she does not need to be an expert in both electronic files and the field-of-use.

51. In other words, as experts on a particular type of electronic file, we can provide a reliable opinion about whether or not a particular file has been modified regardless of the environment in which the electronic file is used.

52. The second misconception that we wish to dispel is the misconception that an expert for determining whether or not a particular paper printout of an alleged electronic document accurately reflects the actual electronic document must also be an expert in the particular field-of-use; he or she does not need to be an expert in both.

53. In other words, as experts on a particular type of electronic file, we can provide a reliable opinion about whether or not a particular paper printout accurately reflects an original electronic file regardless of the environment in which the electronic file is used.

54. The third misconception that we wish to dispel is the misconception that we have been retained as anything other than: **(a)** technical experts with reference to electronic files; and **(b)** legal experts with reference to incompleteness of documents.

55. Thus, to be clear, we are not banking experts; we are not finance experts; we are not sales experts; we are not any other type of expert than what we specifically identify ourselves to be herein, namely, electronic file experts.

56. To be clear, our expertise is electronic files and the completeness of documents.

57. We are qualified to address these commonly held misconceptions because of our knowledge of electronic files and our knowledge of documents.

Specific Background Relating to Uncovering Fabricated Documents, Uncovering Proof of Tampering with Evidence, and Uncovering Anomalies with Electronic Documents

58. Based on our respective education, experience, and training, we have been able to uncover fabricated or manufactured documents in several other cases, uncover tampering with evidence in several other cases, and uncover anomalies with electronic documents.

59. For example, we were the ones that irrefutably proved that National Collegiate Student Loan Trust 2005-2 (hereafter, "NCSLT") had tampered with evidence and then testified falsely to hide its fabrication of documents in *National Collegiate Student Loan Trust 2005-2 v. Peters*, Case Number 2023-CV-03105 (Montgomery County Court of Common Pleas, Ohio) (hereafter, "Peters Case").

60. The step-by-step explanation and documented proof are demonstrated in the following two (2) filings in the Peters Case: **(a)** Defendant's Reply Brief on Defendant's Motion for Summary Judgment, filed on 2024-MAR-20; and **(b)** Defendant's Motion to Sanction Plaintiff and Plaintiff's Counsel for Fraud Upon the Court, filed on 2024-MAR-20.

61. We were also the experts that uncovered discrepancies between a paper printout and its allegedly corresponding electronic file in *LVNV Funding, LLC v. Eric Wiseman*, Case Number 24CV000841 (Franklin County Court of Common Pleas) (hereinafter, "Wiseman Case").

62. The methodology for inspecting and examining electronic documents in the Wiseman Case was actually implemented and applied by Mr. Boyd Gentry (who is counsel of

record in this case), following step-by-step, in near real time, the inspection procedure exactly as instructed on 2024-Dec-17.

63. For example, Gentry himself was able to follow the same process that we apply in examining electronic documents, and Gentry himself observed that: **(a)** the electronic file inspected by Gentry in the Wiseman Case was not even the correct file type; **(b)** the electronic file inspected by Gentry in the Wiseman Case was missing two entire columns that existed in the printed document; **(c)** the electronic file inspected by Gentry in the Wiseman Case had a "Content Created" date that was different from the alleged transaction date; and **(d)** the electronic file inspected by Gentry in the Wiseman Case had columns of data that were out of sequence from the printed document.

64. At a minimum, Gentry himself can confirm that: **(a)** the process that we apply can reliably uncover underlying metadata for electronic files (as Gentry himself did in the Wiseman Case); and **(b)** the process that we apply can reliably uncover any differences between paper copies and alleged original electronic files from which those paper copies are printed, should any such differences exist (as Gentry himself did in the Wiseman Case).

65. We have applied the same rigorous methodology and the same rigorous analysis in this case as we did for the Peters Case and the Wiseman Case.

66. The particular education, training, and experience that is pertinent to our document analysis is our background in electrical engineering and our experience with computers, from which we were able to determine with a reasonable degree of confidence how different document types (e.g., word-processing documents (e.g., ".docx" files), spreadsheets (e.g., ".xlsx" files), portable document format ("PDF") files, etc.) appear in their respective native electronic formats and, further, how those particular documents will appear when printed

to paper from their native electronic formats.

67. Additional education, training, and experience as patent attorneys reinforce our knowledge of the different word-processing, spreadsheet, and other document types.

68. With this salient technological background in mind, our methodology in analyzing the documents for potential fraud or fabrication includes: **(a)** inspecting paper copies of the documents produced to determine whether or not there are any inconsistencies that are readily apparent in the printed (paper) form of the document; **(b)** inspecting any electronic form of the documents (should such electronic documents be available for inspection) from which the paper copies were printed to determine whether or not the printed document is an identical copy of the electronic document; and **(c)** inspecting any underlying metadata of the electronic documents (should such metadata be available) to determine whether or not there has been evidence of tampering or other issues that affect the reliability of the electronic documents.

69. The methodology explained and applied herein for detecting potential fraud or fabrication of documents is a customary and accepted methodology.

Specific Background Relating to Legal Documents

70. Based on our education, experience, and training, we are qualified to provide expert testimony about what is necessary to show a complete and unbroken chain of title.

71. The methodology that we employ for determining a complete and unbroken chain of title is a customary and accepted methodology employed by others in this field.

72. Specifically, we first determine whether or not the documentation is complete.

73. Thereafter, we determine whether or not the chain of title is unbroken.

74. Our methodology for determining whether or not the documentation is complete is by: **(a)** reviewing each document; **(b)** determining whether or not the reviewed document

cross-references another document (hereafter, "cross-referenced document"); (c) listing every cross-referenced document; (d) determining whether or not the cross-referenced document has been produced (or even exists); (e) if the cross-referenced document has been produced, then repeating (a) through (d) for the cross-referenced document.

75. This step-by-step methodology is repeated until, either: (a) all cross-referenced documents are collected; or (b) missing documents are identified.

76. If there are no missing documents, then the conclusion is that the documentation is complete.

77. If there are missing documents, then the conclusion is that the documentation is not complete.

78. Our methodology for determining whether or not the chain of title is unbroken is by tracing forward (from the original owner) every transaction until the last transaction.

79. If there are no gaps from the original owner to the last owner, then the conclusion is that the chain of title is unbroken.

80. If there are gaps from the original owner to the last owner, then the conclusion is that the chain of title is broken.

81. The methodology explained and applied herein for determining completeness and unbrokenness of chain of title is a customary and accepted methodology.

Specific Methodology with Reference to This Report

82. In crafting this Report, we independently reviewed the documents first before consulting with each other.

83. After our respective review of the documents and filings, we consulted each other on the opinions that we formed.

84. As part of our consultation, we questioned each other's opinions and challenged each other's findings so that both of us could be confident in stating our final opinions.

85. In other words, we took an academic process (similar to a peer-review process) that we believed would produce an objective and reasonable opinion.

86. Consequently, this Report reflects what we would consider to be an intellectually honest and objective assessment of the documents, as well as our reasoned explanations for our opinions.

Specific Background for Expert Opinion Relating to Electronic Data Files or Computer Files

87. By way of background for our expert opinion relating to electronic data files or computer files, we note that a spreadsheet, such as Microsoft® Excel® (even when saved as a comma-separated-value file (meaning, with a ".csv" extension)), has cells that contain information or data in various forms.

88. Next, a group of cells can be identified by column (vertically), by row (horizontally), or by a combination of column and row.

89. When a spreadsheet (such as Microsoft® Excel®) is printed, either to paper or to a PDF file, the user is provided with an option to "freeze" the top row (or heading row) so that the headings are preserved on each of the printed pages.

90. If "freeze top row" is not applied, then the headings will only appear on the first page.

91. With all of this background and methodology explained, our opinions (all of which we can state with at least a reasonable degree of certainty) are as follows.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): First Opinion - The Printout Starting with a Column Heading of "FileName" Has Been Deliberately Altered, Destroyed, Concealed, or Otherwise Tampered with to Include Only Twenty-One (21) Lines with Defendant's Entry Being on the Eleventh Line (Line 11)

92. Our first (1st) opinion is that the printout starting with a column headings of "FileName" and "LineNumber" (hereinafter, "Manufactured Printout") is a made-for-litigation document that was fabricated, manufactured, or otherwise generated, either manually (by a person) or automatically (by a computer program or formula or script).

93. The Manufactured Printout begins on line 141977 (circled for clarity) and ends on line 141997 (also circled for clarity), for a total of twenty-one (21) lines, as shown here:

FileName	LineNumber
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141977
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141978
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141979
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141980
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141981
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141982
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141983
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141984
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141985
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141986
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141987
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141988
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141989
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141990
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141991
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141992
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141993
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141994
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141995
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141996
CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023	141997

94. The top row has headings, such as "FileName" and "LineNumber," which demonstrates that "freeze top row" was applied, thereby preserving the heading row for each printed page.

95. Additionally, when a spreadsheet (such as Microsoft® Excel®) is printed to either paper or PDF format, all of the rows are printed sequentially, starting with row "1" and ending with the last row on the spreadsheet.

96. If a single page is too small to contain all of the rows, then a printout of a spreadsheet will continue from page-to-page with each subsequent page starting with a row number that succeeds the last row number of the prior page.

97. Thus, for example, if there are thirty (30) rows printed per page, then the first (1st) page will span rows 1 through 30 (inclusive of rows 1 and 30), the second (2nd) page will span rows 31 through 60 (inclusive of rows 31 and 60), the third (3rd) page will span rows 61 through 90 (inclusive of rows 61 and 90), and so on, until all of the rows in the spreadsheet are printed.

98. Of course, it is possible for the very last page of the document may have fewer rows than the prior pages because the total number of entries in a spreadsheet may not be a clean multiple of the number of rows on each page.

99. Thus, if twenty-one (21) lines are printed on a single page (as it appears to be the case for the Manufactured Printout), then the first page would have rows 1 through 21 (inclusive of rows 1 and 21), the second page would have rows 22 through 42 (inclusive of rows 22 and 42), the third page would have rows 43 through 63 (inclusive of rows 43 and 63), and so on.

100. Ultimately, for a 21 lines-per-page printing, the 6761st page would begin on line 141961 and end on line 141981, while the 6762nd page would begin on line 141982 and end on

line 142002.

101. The following mathematical calculation shows why the 6761st page would begin on line 141961:

$(6760 \text{ pages} \times 21 \text{ lines-per-page}) + 1 \text{ line (for the start of the next page)} = \text{line 141961.}$

102. In other words, in the absence of any altering, destroying, concealing, removing, or otherwise tampering, a printout of a spreadsheet with 21 lines-per-page cannot have a page that begins with line 141977.

103. Instead, a 21-lines-per-page printout would have a page that begins at line 141961 and ends at line 141981 (inclusive of line 141961 and line 141981) or a page that begins at line 141982 and ends at line 142002 (inclusive of line 141982 and line 142002).

104. However, LVNV's Manufactured Printout with twenty-one (21) lines begins at line 141977 and ends at line 141997.

105. There is no reasonable explanation for why LVNV's Manufactured Printout begins at line 141977.

106. Ultimately, our conclusion (based on education, training, and experience), which we can state with at least a reasonable degree of certainty, is that the Manufactured Printout is a document that has been altered, destroyed (to some level), concealed (to some level), or otherwise tampered with in such a way that it has impaired the Manufactured Printout's value or availability as evidence.

107. That altering, destroying, concealing, or otherwise tampering with the Manufactured Printout was done either manually or by a computer program that was specifically designed to print twenty-one (21) lines per page to make it appear as if it was a portion of a larger total printout.

108. We have observed this same type of altering, destroying, concealing, or otherwise tampering with evidence in other LVNV cases.

109. If LVNV provides an unmodified electronic copy of the original electronic or computer file, with metadata intact, then we can demonstrate any altering, destroying, concealing, removing, or otherwise tampering with the Manufactured Printout.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Second Opinion - The Manufactured Printout Is Not a Redacted Version of an Original Spreadsheet But, Rather, a Spreadsheet in Which Specific Cells Have Been Deliberately Altered, Either Manually or Through a Computer Program That Was Specifically Designed to Alter Information Within Cells

110. Our second (2nd) opinion is that the Manufactured Printout has been deliberately altered, either manually or through a computer program that was designed to alter information within a cell.

111. We arrive at this conclusion because there are inconsistencies within the document that cannot be reasonably explained.

112. For example, there are at least four (4) different types of redactions.

113. The first type of alleged redaction is an entire cell being replaced by a text string that recites "[Redacted]" (shown here and circled for clarity):

114. The second type of alleged redaction is an entire cell being covered by a black box, as shown here (circled for clarity):

115. The third type of alleged redaction is a partial cell being covered by a black box, as shown here (circled for clarity):

116. The fourth type of alleged redaction is part of the cell reciting "[Redacted]" followed by a four (4) digit number (see, e.g., "[Redacted]7142" and "[Redacted]8571"), as shown here (circled for clarity):

117. We find it peculiar (and not reasonably explainable) that there are four (4) different types of redactions in a single document.

118. Having used spreadsheets for several decades, and being familiar with how spreadsheets operate based on our experience, education, and training, we are not aware of any provision or formula (for example, native to Microsoft® Excel®) that redacts a cell by replacing its contents with "[Redacted]" (whether completely or partially).

119. In other words, we are not aware of any redaction features that display a cell as "[Redacted]" unless the cell has been specifically populated with a text entry of "[Redacted]."

120. We are aware of only one (1) way in which a cell can be displayed with "[Redacted]" in the cell, which is by inserting the text "[Redacted]" in the cell (whether

completely or partially).

121. Based on our experience, education, and training, all of the cells with entries that show "[Redacted]" were either manually populated with "[Redacted]" or a computer program (or a formula or a script) was used to populate those cells with "[Redacted]."

122. Next, we also find it peculiar that there are at least two (2) cells in which a dollar value is shown up to four (4) decimal places (meaning, to the nearest 1/10,000th of a dollar (or 1/100th of a cent))

123. This is shown in the columns labeled as "Cur_Bal" (presumably for current balance) and "LastPurchaseAmount" (showing up to four (4) decimal places, circled for clarity):

Cur_Bal	LastPurchaseAmount
[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1977.5600	30.6900
[Redacted]	[Redacted]

124. Having used spreadsheets for several decades, and being familiar with how spreadsheets display American currency values, we are not aware of any features that display up to four (4) decimal places for dollar values.

125. Another anomaly in the Manufactured Printout is the existence of at least three (3) different date formats.

126. The first date format is m/d/yyyy (month first), as shown here (circled for clarity):

CODT	LPAYDT
[Redacted]	[Redacted]
12/20/2022	5/11/2022
[Redacted]	[Redacted]

127. The second date format is dd-MMM-yyyy (day first and with hyphens), as shown here (circled for clarity):

LastPreCOPayment_Date
[Redacted]
11-MAY-2022
[Redacted]

128. The third date format is ddMMMyyyy (day first but without hyphens), as shown here (circled for clarity):

LastPurchaseDate
[Redacted]
04MAY2022
[Redacted]

129. There is no reasonable explanation for why there should be three (3) different formats for dates in the same document.

130. Next, and most significantly, in the Manufactured Printout is the existence of different number formats for dollar values.

131. For example, some dollar values are shown with a leading currency symbol ("\$\$"), while other dollar values completely omit the currency symbol.

132. For comparison, the same dollar amount has different formats between "HIGHBALANCE" and "Cur_Bal" (presumably for "current balance"), shown here side-by-side for comparison:

HIGHBALANCE	Cur_Bal
[Redacted]	[Redacted]
\$1,977.56	1977.5600
[Redacted]	[Redacted]

133. The first difference is that "Cur_Bal" shows the currency to the 1/100th of a penny (see, **.5600** dollars), but "HIGHBALANCE" has the expected number of decimal places (to the nearest penny (see, **.56** dollars), shown side-by-side with difference circled for clarity:

Cur_Bal	HIGHBALANCE
[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1977. 5600	\$1,977. 56
[Redacted]	[Redacted]

136. The same inconsistent formatting without and with the currency symbol ("\$\$") manifests itself in "LPAYAMT" and "LastPreCO_Payment", which are exactly the same dollar amount (shown here without any markings and, also, with discrepancy circled for clarity):

LPAYAMT	LastPreCO_Payment	LPAYAMT	LastPreCO_Payment
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
71.00	\$71.00	71.00	\$71.00
[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

137. Even cells that are side-by-side have this inconsistency (as shown here with one column with "0.00" (without dollar symbol) followed by another column with "\$0.00" (with dollar symbol)):

TotalPostCOPayments	TotalMerchPostCOCharges
[Redacted]	[Redacted]
0.00	\$0.00
[Redacted]	[Redacted]

138. There is no reasonable explanation for using inconsistent formats for currency

(meaning, with a leading "\$" and without a leading symbol, with a radix character (",") and without a radix character, showing two (2) decimal places and also four (4) decimal places).

139. This is because using different formats for the same type of data can lead to errors when computing operations are performed on the same type of data.

140. In other words, as those with an electrical engineering or a computer science background know, an attempt to add a text string with a number can lead to unexpected errors that can be caused because of the different data types.

141. Thus, our second (2nd) opinion is that the Manufactured Printout is a spreadsheet in which information in specific cells have been deliberately altered, destroyed, concealed, removed, or otherwise tampered with to have different formats for the same data types.

142. That deliberate alteration, destruction, concealment, removal, or otherwise tampering of the contents of certain cells was done either manually or through a computer program that was specifically designed to alter the information within those particular cells.

143. If LVNV provides an unmodified electronic copy, with metadata intact, then we can confirm whether or not the underlying data demonstrates altering, destroying, concealing, removing, or otherwise tampering of the Manufactured Printout.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Third Opinion - The "Receivable File" Referenced in the Alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Accounts from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" and the Alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Receivables from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" Cannot be the Same as the "Receivable File dated January 04, 2023" Referenced in the Alleged "Transfer and Assignment" Document

144. Our third (3rd) opinion is that the "Computer File" referenced in the alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Accounts from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" (which alleged transferred (past tense) "Accounts" on 2022-Dec-31) and the alleged "Bill of Sale

and Assignment of Receivables from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" (which allegedly transferred (past tense) "Receivables" on 2022-Dec-31) cannot be the same as the "Receivable File dated January 04, 2023" referenced in the alleged "Transfer and Assignment."

145. The basis of our opinion is that the 2022-Dec-31 transfer could not have referenced a document that came into existence on 2023-Jan-04.

146. Here, the alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Accounts from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" shows, in relevant part (and circled for clarity):

BILL OF SALE AND ASSIGNMENT OF ACCOUNTS
FROM CREDIT ONE BANK, N.A. TO MHC RECEIVABLES, LLC

As of December 31, 2022, for good and valuable consideration, the receipt and sufficiency of which is hereby acknowledged, Credit One Bank, N.A. ("Assignor") has transferred, has sold, has assigned, has conveyed, has granted and has otherwise delivered to MHC Receivables, LLC ("Assignee"), all of Assignor's right, title and interest in and to (i) the charged-off credit card accounts identified on an account level basis in the data file named CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023 (the "Computer File"), a copy of which is attached hereto and incorporated herein by reference as "Exhibit A"; and, (ii) certain related account level media or electronic copies thereof (including, but not limited to applications, statements, terms and condition), and (iii) all claims or rights arising out of or relating to each account referenced on the Computer File (collectively hereinafter, the "Accounts") including, but not limited to, all claims and rights afforded each Account by virtue of that Account's corresponding terms and conditions.

147. Specifically, a "Computer File" is referenced and expressly noted as being attached as "Exhibit A."

148. "Exhibit A" to the "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Accounts from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" shows (with filename circled for clarity):

EXHIBIT A

ACCOUNT SCHEDULE

The Accounts that are specifically identified in the electronic file named CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023 with such electronic file incorporated herein by reference.

149. The alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Receivables from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" also shows, in relevant part (and circled for clarity):

BILL OF SALE AND ASSIGNMENT OF RECEIVABLES
FROM CREDIT ONE BANK, N.A. TO MHC RECEIVABLES, LLC

As of December 31, 2022 for good and valuable consideration, the receipt and sufficiency of which is hereby acknowledged, Credit One Bank, N.A. ("Assignor") has transferred, has sold, has assigned, has conveyed, has granted and has otherwise delivered to MHC Receivables, LLC ("Assignee"), all of Assignor's right, title and interest in and to (i) the receivables associated with each and every account referenced in the data file named CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023 (the "Computer File"), a copy of which is attached hereto and incorporated herein by reference as "Exhibit A"; and, (ii) all claims or rights arising out of or relating to each of those Receivables (hereinafter, the "Receivables").

150. Here, there is also a "Computer File" referenced and expressly noted as being attached as "Exhibit A."

151. "Exhibit A" to the "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Receivables from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" shows (with filename circled for clarity):

EXHIBIT A

ACCOUNT SCHEDULE

The Accounts that are specifically identified in the electronic file named CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023 with such electronic file incorporated herein by reference.

152. Oddly, rather than stating that the "Receivables" are specifically identified, this "Exhibit A" also states that the "Accounts" are specifically identified, thereby being inconsistent with the "Receivables" recitation in the "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Receivables from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC."

153. Ultimately, both alleged transfers from Credit One Bank, N.A. (which is allegedly the original creditor) specifically state that "[a]s of December 31, 2022" Credit One Bank, N.A. "has transferred, has sold, has assigned, has conveyed, has granted and has otherwise delivered to MHC Receivables, LLC . . ." (all in the past tense).

154. Both alleged transfers also reference the "Computer File" with a file name

"CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023."

155. The alleged "Transfer and Assignment" document (which allegedly transfers assets to LVNV) states that "Exhibit A" is "the Receivable File dated January 04, 2023" (circled for clarity):

Transfer and Assignment

Resurgent Acquisitions LLC ("RALLC"), without recourse, to the extent permitted by applicable law, hereby transfers, sells, assigns, conveys, grants and delivers to LVNV Funding LLC ("LVNV") all of its right, title and interest in and to the receivables and other assets (the "Assets") identified on Exhibit A, in the Receivable File dated January 04, 2023 delivered by Credit Asset Sales LLC on January 18, 2023 for purchase by RALLC on January 18, 2023. The transfer of the Assets included electronically stored business records.

156. The "Receivable File dated January 04, 2023" (emphasis supplied) is identified on Exhibit A, as shown here (filename circled for clarity):

Exhibit A		
Receivables File		
01.18.23	<u>CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023</u>	
Transfer Group	Portfolio	Transfer Batch
883587	41223	N/A

157. In other words, the "CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023" file that is referenced in both the alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Accounts from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" and the alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Receivables from Credit One Bank, N.A. to MHC Receivables, LLC" cannot be the same "CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023" file that is referenced in the alleged "Transfer and Assignment" because it is impossible for a file that is "dated January 04, 2023" to have existed (in the past tense) on "December 31, 2022."

158. Thus, our third (3rd) opinion is that the "Computer File" referenced in the alleged

2022-Dec-31 transfers cannot be the same as the "Receivable File dated January 04, 2023" referenced in the 2023-Jan-18 "Transfer and Assignment."

159. If we are provided with the original electronic files, un-redacted and with all of the metadata intact, then we can review the metadata (precisely as Gentry had done in accordance with our instructed procedures in the Wiseman Case) to: **(a)** confirm or refute that the provided electronic files are indeed the ones from the alleged 2022-Dec-31 transfer (meaning, those files are the ones that actually existed prior to 2022-Dec-31); and **(b)** confirm or refute that the provided electronic files are indeed the ones from the alleged 2023-Jan-18 transfer (meaning, the files "dated January 04, 2023").

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Fourth Opinion - The Chain of Title Is Incomplete Because the Referenced "Purchase and Sale Agreement . . . Dated as of January 1, 2022" Is Missing

160. Our fourth (4th) opinion is that the chain of title is incomplete because the referenced "Purchase and Sale Agreement, by and between Seller and Resurgent Acquisitions LLC ('Buyer'), dated as of January 1, 2022 ('Agreement')" is missing.

161. This missing file is significant because the alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Accounts and Receivables from Credit Asset Sales LLC to Resurgent Acquisitions LLC" expressly: **(a)** references a "Purchase and Sale Agreement"; **(b)** states that the alleged transaction is "in accordance with the terms of the Purchase and Sale Agreement"; **(c)** states that the alleged "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Accounts and Receivables is subject to the terms of the Agreement"; and **(d)** disclaims all "representations and warranties of any kind or character except as expressly stated in the Agreement."

162. These material terms are shown here (circled for clarity):

**BILL OF SALE AND ASSIGNMENT OF ACCOUNTS AND RECEIVABLES
FROM CREDIT ASSET SALES LLC TO RESURGENT ACQUISITIONS LLC**

Credit Asset Sales LLC ("Seller"), the owner of certain accounts and associated receivables (hereinafter referred to collectively as "Purchased Accounts"), for value received and in accordance with the terms of the Purchase and Sale Agreement, by and between Seller and Resurgent Acquisitions LLC. ("Buyer"), dated as of January 1, 2022 ("Agreement"), does hereby sell, assign and transfer to Buyer, its successors and assigns, all right, title and interest in and to the Purchased Accounts as described on the computer file named CreditOne_Fresh_Resurgent_012023 (the "Computer File"), a copy of which is attached hereto and incorporated herein by reference as "Exhibit A".

This Bill of Sale and Assignment of Accounts and Receivables is subject to the terms of the Agreement and is made without representations and warranties of any kind or character except as expressly stated in the Agreement or as expressly stated below.

163. Without the "Purchase and Sale Agreement . . . dated January 1, 2022 ('Agreement')," one cannot determine whether or not: **(a)** any alleged "Purchased Accounts" were properly sold, assigned, or transferred; **(b)** any precondition or condition precedent, which were "subject to the terms of the Agreement" had been met for a proper sale, assignment, or transfer.

164. If we are provided with the original, un-redacted "Purchase and Sale Agreement" from "January 1, 2022," then we can review that document to determine the completeness of the alleged transfer documents in accordance with the procedure that we describe herein.

Concluding Remarks

165. If original, unmodified electronic documents are provided for review, then we can provide a more accurate assessment of how, precisely, the documents were created, stored, transferred, or otherwise manipulated over time.

166. Even in the absence of the original, electronic files, we can (at least reasonably) conclude that one (1) or more documents are fabricated, manufactured, altered, or subjected to tampering.

167. In other words, although the production of the original, electronic files may show how the documents were fabricated, manufactured, altered, or subjected to tampering, what those original, electronic files will not be able to explain are the inconsistencies that we note herein

(which cannot be reasonably explained based on how computers work).

168. Consequently, it is our opinion (based on our education, training, and experience) that the statements by LVNV that it owns an alleged debt is based on fabricated documents, modified documents, and missing documents, all of which constitute false and misleading statements.

169. Furthermore, insofar as counsel for LVNV (Mr. Boyd Gentry) has been able to implement or apply our procedure for inspecting electronic documents, and insofar as Mr. Gentry's application of the procedure demonstrated the results that we ourselves expected to uncover from the inspection, we can say with a reasonable degree of confidence that our procedure can reliably and repeatedly be applied for inspection of electronic documents, irrespective of the environment in which the electronic documents are used.

170. Lastly, to avoid any dispute on the results or outcome of our described procedure, we are agreeable to demonstrating our procedure in person and in near real time before LVNV's counsel, just as we did in the Wiseman Case.

171. If LVNV produces the original electronic documents, un-redacted and in native electronic format with all of the metadata intact, then we are also agreeable to demonstrating the metadata inspection procedure before the Court to dispel any commonly held misconceptions that such an inspection requires education, training, or experience in the fields of finance, banking, accounts receivable management, or the sale of default receivables (rather than expertise in electronic files).

172. We reserve the right to amend any statements herein, should new information become available (such as a late-filed expert report by LVNV, or late-produced documents that LVNV previously alleged to be irrelevant that LVNV must now produce to overcome the facts

recited herein).

FURTHER DECLARANT SAYETH NAUGHT.

[SIGNATURE AND OATH TO FOLLOW]

Executed on 2025-JAN-24, in Dayton, Ohio.

Sam Han

(for: (a) joint portions; and (b) portions that are labeled as pertaining to Sam Han)

Brian Sullivan

(for: (a) joint portions; and (b) portions that are labeled as pertaining to Brian Sullivan)

STATE OF OHIO, ||
MONTGOMERY COUNTY || SS:

Sworn to and subscribed in my presence this 24 day of January, 2025.

Therese M. Mohs
Notary Public

THERESE MARIE MOHS
Notary Public
State of Ohio
My Comm. Expires
December 29, 2029